

Interaction Studies in Binary Liquid Mixtures of Polar and Non-polar Solvents from Viscosity Data

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An attempt has been made to compare the relative merits of Frenkel, Ubbelohde, Naidu and Katti-Chaudhuri relations for the theoretical evaluation of viscosity in binary liquid mixtures of acetone and methyl ethyl ketone with non-polar solvents cyclohexane, benzene, *p*-xylene and mesitylene. Furthermore, the study has been extended to investigate the intermolecular interaction in terms of excess free energy of mixing. The nature of interaction has been discussed in detail.

PIONEERING attempts have been made by several workers¹⁻¹⁰ to study the interaction in the binary liquid mixtures using thermodynamic excess functions. But only a few¹¹⁻¹⁵ have used the viscosity data for this purpose. The aim of the present investigation is two-fold: firstly, to compare the relative merits of Frenkel¹⁶, Hind *et al.*¹⁷, Naidu¹⁸ and Katti-*et al.*^{11,12} relations for the theoretical evaluation of viscosity in binary liquid mixtures, and secondly, to evaluate excess free energy of mixing ($\alpha \Delta G_m$) and to discuss intermolecular interactions in the light of free energy of mixing.

Theoretical: The following relation¹⁹ has been given for the actual value of fluidity of the mixture,

$$\phi_m(a) = \frac{V_m}{hN}$$

$$\exp - \left\{ \left[(x_1 \Delta E_1 + x_2 \Delta E_2) / 2.45 - \frac{\Delta G_m}{2.45} \right] / RT \right\} \quad (1)$$

where, $\phi_m(a)$ = fluidity of the mixture, V_m = molar volume of the mixture, h = Planck's constant, N = Avagadro's number, ΔE_1 and ΔE_2 = energy of vaporisation of the components whose mole fractions are x_1 and x_2 , respectively, ΔG_m = excess free energy of mixing, k = gas constant, and T = temperature in absolute. Rewriting the above equation in terms of viscosity of the mixture [$\eta_m(a)$] and taking logarithm on both sides, one gets,

$$\ln \eta_m(a) + \ln \frac{V_m}{hN} = \left(\frac{x_1 \Delta E_1 + x_2 \Delta E_2}{2.45 RT} \right) - \frac{\alpha \Delta G_m}{RT} \quad (2)$$

The fraction 1/2.45 of the excess free energy of mixing in equation (1) has been represented by α in equation (2). But remembering that $\Delta G^* = \Delta G / 2.45$

(energy of activation), the viscosity of ideal mixture in the light of equation

$$\phi_m(i) = \frac{V}{hN} \exp \{ -(x_1 \Delta G_1^* + x_2 \Delta G_2^*) / RT \} \quad (3)$$

takes the following form,

$$\ln \eta_m(i) + \ln \frac{V}{hN} = \frac{x_1 \Delta E_1 + x_2 \Delta E_2}{2.45 RT} \quad (4)$$

and from equations (3) and (4) one obtains,

$$\alpha \Delta G_m = -RT [\ln \eta_m(a) - \ln \eta_m(i)] \quad (5)$$

Katti *et al.*¹² proposed the following equation for the theoretical evaluation of viscosity,

$$\ln \eta_m(a) = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 \frac{W_{12}}{RT} \quad (6)$$

where, W_{12} represents the interaction energy between the components. Hind *et al.*¹⁷ used the following expression for the viscosity of a liquid mixture,

$$\eta_{12} = x_1^2 \eta_1 + 2x_1 x_2 \eta_{12} + x_2^2 \eta_2 \quad (7)$$

where, η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of pure liquid components whose mole fractions are x_1 and x_2 , and η_{12} is the viscosity at equimolar concentrations. The value of η_{12} is obtained by the relation,

$$\eta_{12} = 0.5 \eta_{(m)1} + 0.5 \eta_{(m)2}$$

This value of η_{12} is used to obtain η_m at other compositions.

The viscosity of a liquid mixture according to Frenkel¹⁰ and Naidu¹⁸ is obtained by the following two different equations, respectively,

$$\log \eta_m(a) = x_1 \log \eta_1 + x_2 \log \eta_2 + 2x_1x_2 \log \eta_{12} \quad (8)$$

$$\ln \eta_m = x_1^2 \ln \eta_1 + x_2^2 \ln \eta_2 + 2x_1x_2 \ln \eta_{12} \quad (9)$$

Results and Discussion

The viscosity of the binary liquid mixtures of acetone and methyl ethyl ketone with non-polar solvents cyclohexane, benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene and mesitylene, evaluated by different theoretical equations, has been compared with the experimental value in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The necessary data for the evaluation of viscosity have been taken from the measurement made by Yadava and Yadava²⁰. A perusal of Tables 1 and 2 indi-

cates that for the liquid mixtures of acetone+cyclohexane, and methyl ethyl ketone+cyclohexane, Frenkel relation gives values more comparable with the experimental values of viscosity than Hind *et al.*, Naidu and Katti *et al.* relations. But for the systems acetone+aromatics, and methyl ethyl ketone+aromatics, the viscosities evaluated by other three relations are better than Frenkel relation.

The excess free energy of mixing ($\alpha\Delta G_m$) calculated on the basis of experimental values of viscosity have been enlisted in the last columns of Tables 1 and 2. The values of $\alpha\Delta G_m$ indicate that they are greater for the mixtures with cyclohexane and the mixtures with aromatics. So it seems that in the case of polar solute+cyclohexane binary mixtures, the forces between pairs of unlike molecules are far less as compared to the forces between

TABLE 1—THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL VALUE OF VISCOSITY (η) AND EXCESS FREE ENERGY OF MIXING ($\alpha\Delta G_m$) OF BINARY MIXTURES OF ACETONE WITH NON-POLAR SOLVENT AND WITH CYCLOHEXANE AT 307.35 K

Mole fraction of acetone (x_2)	Values of viscosity (η) ($\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)					$\alpha\Delta G_m$ from expt. (kJ mol^{-1})
	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Expt.)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Frenkel's eq 8)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Ubbelohde's eq 7)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Naidu's eq 9)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Katti-Chaudhuri's eq. 6)	
Acetone + Cyclohexane						
0.000 0	0.076					
0.091 0	0.066	0.063	0.072	0.071	0.072	0.204 7
0.311 6	0.051	0.043	0.061	0.059	0.061	0.462 2
0.394 9	0.046	0.038	0.057	0.055	0.057	0.562 1
0.458 9	0.043	0.035	0.054	0.052	0.054	0.596 5
0.529 9	0.040	0.033	0.051	0.048	0.050	0.612 7
0.789 7	0.032	0.029	0.039	0.037	0.038	0.473 9
1.000 0	0.029					
Acetone + Benzene						
0.000 0	0.053					
0.111 5	0.049	0.042	0.050	0.050	0.051	0.057 5
0.357 3	0.042	0.028	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.149 3
0.493 8	0.038	0.025	0.041	0.040	0.040	0.190 1
0.556 2	0.037	0.024	0.040	0.039	0.039	0.149 3
0.646 4	0.035	0.024	0.036	0.037	0.037	0.161 1
0.885 3	0.031	0.026	0.032	0.031	0.032	0.077 6
1.000 0	0.029					
Acetone + <i>p</i> -Xylene						
0.000 0	0.054					
0.140 3	0.050	0.040	0.050	0.050	0.051	0.020 9
0.430 0	0.043	0.027	0.043	0.042	0.044	0.016 0
0.576 8	0.040	0.025	0.040	0.039	0.041	-0.030 0
0.629 8	0.038	0.024	0.038	0.037	0.039	-0.018 7
0.728 5	0.035	0.024	0.036	0.035	0.037	0.033 1
0.911 8	0.031	0.027	0.031	0.031	0.032	0.008 2
1.000 0	0.029					
Acetone + Mesitylene						
0.000 0	0.058					
0.138 7	0.054	0.044	0.054	0.054	0.055	0.010 4
0.449 3	0.045	0.028	0.045	0.045	0.047	0.027 9
0.597 5	0.040	0.026	0.041	0.041	0.043	0.033 4
0.656 7	0.038	0.025	0.039	0.039	0.041	0.052 2
0.752 1	0.036	0.025	0.036	0.036	0.038	0.006 3
0.916 8	0.031	0.027	0.031	0.031	0.032	0.012 2
1.000 0	0.029					

TABLE 2—THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF VISCOSITY (η) AND EXCESS FREE ENERGY OF MIXING ($\alpha\Delta G_m$) OF BINARY MIXTURES OF METHYL ETHYL KETONE WITH NON-POLAR SOLVENT AND WITH CYCLOHEXANE AT 307.35 K

Mole fraction of methyl ethyl ketone (x_1)	Values of viscosity (η) ($\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)					$\alpha\Delta G_m$ from expt. (kJ mol^{-1})
	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Expt.)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Frenkel's eq. 8)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Ubbelohde's eq. 7)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Naidu's eq. 9)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Katti-Chaudhuri's eq. 6)	
Methyl ethyl ketone + Cyclohexane						
0.000 0	0.076					
0.109 3	0.065	0.062	0.072	0.071	0.071	0.252 2
0.361 0	0.050	0.044	0.061	0.059	0.060	0.496 2
0.497 5	0.045	0.039	0.056	0.054	0.054	0.523 6
0.555 0	0.043	0.037	0.053	0.051	0.052	0.551 8
0.680 9	0.041	0.035	0.048	0.046	0.046	0.388 5
0.886 5	0.037	0.034	0.040	0.039	0.039	0.204 6
1.000 0	0.035					
Methyl ethyl ketone + Benzene						
0.000 0	0.053					
0.092 5	0.050	0.044	0.051	0.051	0.051	0.062 0
0.240 5	0.046	0.036	0.049	0.048	0.048	0.133 1
0.317 8	0.045	0.033	0.047	0.047	0.047	0.149 1
0.447 7	0.042	0.029	0.045	0.045	0.044	0.148 7
0.508 4	0.041	0.029	0.044	0.043	0.043	0.171 8
0.616 0	0.039	0.028	0.042	0.042	0.041	0.157 8
0.735 6	0.038	0.028	0.040	0.039	0.039	0.129 2
1.000 0	0.035					
Methyl ethyl ketone + <i>p</i> -Xylene						
0.000 0	0.054					
0.127 3	0.052	0.043	0.052	0.051	0.052	-0.000 5
0.311 0	0.048	0.033	0.048	0.048	0.048	0.001 1
0.394 9	0.046	0.031	0.046	0.046	0.047	0.041 1
0.532 6	0.043	0.029	0.044	0.043	0.044	0.025 2
0.591 3	0.042	0.028	0.043	0.042	0.043	0.049 5
0.694 9	0.040	0.028	0.041	0.040	0.041	0.042 3
0.787 1	0.039	0.029	0.039	0.039	0.039	0.014 5
1.000 0	0.035					
Methyl ethyl ketone + Mesitylene						
0.000 0	0.058					
0.125 6	0.055	0.046	0.056	0.055	0.056	0.025 9
0.326 6	0.050	0.035	0.051	0.050	0.052	0.038 6
0.417 5	0.048	0.033	0.049	0.048	0.050	0.038 7
0.558 1	0.044	0.030	0.045	0.045	0.046	0.059 3
0.621 3	0.043	0.030	0.044	0.043	0.045	0.062 5
0.713 3	0.041	0.030	0.042	0.041	0.043	0.050 1
0.801 9	0.039	0.030	0.040	0.039	0.040	0.047 5
0.903 5	0.039	0.032	0.037	0.037	0.038	-0.091 0
1.000 0	0.035					

pairs of like molecules, and that is why the mixture is less viscous and hence $\alpha\Delta G_m$ for these systems is comparatively larger. This is perhaps due to dipole-induced dipole interaction proportional to the polarisability of the aromatic molecule. Since *p*-xylene and mesitylene molecules are more polarisable than benzene, increased interaction of the polar solute with the former two aromatic solvents and hence the lower values of excess free energy of mixing for their mixtures as compared to those with benzene, is quite anticipated.

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